

Structure and bonding in ternary and quaternary transition metal carbides and carbide silicides containing linear M=C=M units

R. Bruce King

Department of Chemistry, University of Georgia, Athens, Georgia 30602, U.S.A.

E-mail : rbking@sunchem.chem.uga.edu

Manuscript received 10 October 2000

Linear infinite chains of Co=C=Co units are found in the structure of LnCoC derivatives (Ln = Y or lanthanides). Similar linear M=C=M units can be used to construct the infinite two-dimensional networks of Ln₂M₂C₃ structures (M = Cr, Mo). In addition linear M=C=M units link the double butterfly chains in the quaternary metal carbide silicides Ln₂M₂Si₂C and LnM₂SiC. This paper discusses chemical bonding, electron counting, and formal metal oxidation states in these solid state structures.

One of the major developments in chemistry during the second half of the twentieth century has been the discovery of a variety of molecular transition metal organometallic compounds containing metal-carbon bonds of diverse types¹. These developments were stimulated by the serendipitous discovery of ferrocene in 1951^{2,3} which led to the recognition that an organic π -system could form a chemical bond with a transition metal using all of the carbon atoms of the π -system, e.g. 5 or 6 carbon atoms in the case of cyclopentadienyl or benzene, respectively. Subsequent work led to the discovery of compounds clearly containing metal-carbon multiple bonds. The first recognized examples of such compounds were the carbene complexes (RO)R'C=Cr(CO)₅ first reported by Fischer and Maasbol in 1964⁴, which clearly contain Cr=C double bonds.

Solid state chemistry has also developed extensively in recent years. Of particular interest in the context of organometallic chemistry has been the discovery of ternary and quaternary transition metal carbides which are indicated by their interatomic distances to contain metal-carbon bonds related to those found in molecular transition metal organometallic compounds^{5,6}. In such ternary transition metal carbides the element other than carbon and the transition metal is a highly electropositive multivalent metal such as a lanthanide (abbreviated as Ln), yttrium or thorium. Complete ionization of the electropositive metal to the stable ions Ln³⁺, Y³⁺, or Th⁴⁺ leads to a negatively charged transition metal-carbon subnetwork, which may be considered to be an organometallic net. Such ternary metal carbides, as well as related more complicated quaternary carbides, can thus be regarded as negatively charged organometallic polymers imbedded in a matrix of positive ions. In many of these ternary transition metal carbides the transition metal can be assigned a low formal oxidation states reminiscent of the

metal oxidation states in metal carbonyls and metal-olefin complexes¹.

These ternary and quaternary transition metal carbides are refractory materials, which have been synthesized by reactions at temperatures far higher than the decomposition temperatures of the most thermally stable molecular transition metal organometallic compounds. Nevertheless, a few of the refractory transition metal carbides have structures apparently containing transition metal-carbon *double* bonds. The first recognized example of such metal-carbon double bonding in a carbide appears to be YCoC which contains an infinite =C=Co=C= linear chain arising from polymerization of CoC_{2/2}⁻ repeating units^{7,8}. Subsequently, other solid state carbides containing related M=C=M units were discovered including the ternary carbides Ln₂ReC₂ (Ref. 9) and Ln₂M₂C₃ (M = Cr, Mo)¹⁰⁻¹³ as well as the quaternary carbide silicides Ln₂Fe₂Si₂C (Ref. 14) and LnFe₂SiC (Ref. 15). This paper surveys the structure and chemical bonding in these solid state materials.

Ternary metal carbides YCoC and Y₂ReC₂

In ternary metal carbides such as YCoC and Y₂ReC₂ electron donation from a carbon atom to the transition metal leads to formation of a metal-carbon double bond, necessarily with both a σ and a π component. The M=C π -bonding uses a *p*-orbital excluded from the σ -bonding valence orbital of the transition metal so that the actual dimensionality of the transition metal valence orbital manifold is one higher than that used exclusively for the σ -bonding (Fig. 1)^{5,6}.

The anionic cobalt-carbon subnetwork in YCoC consists of =C=Co=C=Co=C= infinite chains with 16 electrons per CoC_{2/2}⁻ repeating unit (Fig. 1a)⁷. Each cobalt

Fig. 1. (a) The $\text{CoC}_{2/2}^{3-}$ repeating unit in YCoC , (b) The $\text{ReCC}_{2/2}^{6-}$ repeating unit in Y_2ReC_2

atom is thus bonded to two carbon atoms in linear coordination. The central cobalt atom in a $\text{CoC}_{2/2}^{3-}$ repeating unit has the $9(\text{Co}) + 4(=\text{C}) + 3(-3 \text{ charge}) = 16$ electrons required to fill an eight-orbital toroidal sp^2d^5 manifold consisting of the seven-orbital spd^5 manifold plus another p -orbital for the π -component of a $\text{Co}=\text{C}$ double bond. Assignment of the usual +3 and -4 oxidation states to Y^{3+} and C^{4-} in YCoC leads to a formal +1 oxidation state for the cobalt atom. If the $\text{Co}=\text{C}$ double bonds to the $=\text{C}=\text{}$ ligands are replaced by equivalent bent $\text{Co}-\text{C}$ single bonds ('banana bonds'), then the cobalt atom in YCoC may be considered to have square-planar coordination which is typical for d^8 transition metals such as Co^1 . Extended Hückel calculations⁸ confirm the existence of extensive π -bonding in the $[\text{CoC}_{2/2}^{3-}]_{\infty}$ infinite chains in YCoC .

The anionic rhenium-carbon network in Y_2ReC_2 , like that of YCoC , consists of $=\text{C}=\text{Re}=\text{C}=\text{Re}=\text{C}$ infinite chains (Fig. 1b)⁹. However, each rhenium atom is bonded to three carbon atoms in approximate trigonal planar coordination rather than only two carbon atoms as is the case in YCoC . For this reason, the $=\text{C}=\text{Re}=\text{C}=\text{Re}=\text{C}$ infinite chains are zigzag rather than strictly linear as in YCoC . Two of the three carbon atoms are the bridging carbon atoms and the third carbon atom is a terminal carbon atom so that the repeating units in the rhenium-carbon subnetwork of Y_2ReC_2 can be considered to be $\text{ReC}_{2/2}\text{C}^{6-}$ with 21 electrons per repeating unit. The $\text{Re}=\text{C}$ bond lengths in Y_2ReC_2 are 1.72 and 2.34 Å to the bridging $=\text{C}=\text{}$ atom and 2.13 Å to the terminal C atom suggesting that the $\text{Re}=\text{C}$ bond order to the terminal carbon atom is no lower than the average $\text{Re}=\text{C}$ bond order to the bridging carbon atoms implying that all three $\text{Re}=\text{C}$ bonds are double bonds. Elementary group theory¹⁶ indicates that the rhenium $sp^3d^2(xz,yz)$ orbitals can form three trigonally hybridized σ -bonds to the three carbon atoms as well as one π -bond to each carbon atom perpendicular to the ReC_3 plane. This $sp^3d^2(xz,yz)$ orbital set

for the rhenium atom is the same as the set of metal orbitals that are used for the trigonal prismatic hybridization if two 'banana' bonds from the rhenium to each carbon atom are used instead of the $\sigma + \pi(\perp)$ pairs. The central rhenium atom in an $\text{ReC}_{2/2}\text{C}^{6-}$ unit in Y_2ReC_2 has a 17-electron configuration obtained as follows :

Neutral rhenium atom	7 electrons
2/2 bridging ($\text{Re}=\text{C}=\text{}$) ligand (2/2) (4) =	4 electrons
1 terminal ($\text{Re}=\text{C}$ ligand (1) (0) =	0 electrons
-6 charge	6 electrons
Total valence electrons per Re atom	17 electrons

This 17-electron configuration for the central rhenium atoms is one less than the favored 18-electron noble gas configuration. However, the minimum $\text{Re}\dots\text{Re}$ distances are too long for any significant rhenium-rhenium bonding. Assignment of the usual +3 and -4 oxidation states to the yttrium and carbon atoms in Y_2ReC_2 leads to a formal +2 oxidation state for its rhenium atoms.

Ternary metal carbides of the type $\text{Ln}_2\text{M}_2\text{C}_3$ (M = Cr, Mo)

Ternary metal carbides containing Group-6 transition metals of the stoichiometries $\text{Ln}_2\text{M}_2\text{C}_3$ (M = Cr, Mo) also have structures constructed from linear $\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{M}$ units. The structures of the transition metal-carbon subnetworks in $\text{Ln}_2\text{M}_2\text{C}_3$ (Fig. 2) can be constructed from double chains of $=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{}$ units linked also by $\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{M}$ units. The carbon atoms in $\text{Ln}_2\text{M}_2\text{C}_3$ are of two different types, namely, the carbons in the original single $=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{}$ chains (2/3 of the total carbons) and the carbons in the $\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{M}$ units linking the $=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{}$ chains (1/3 of the total carbons). Further linking of the double chains can occur by formation of metal-metal bonds and redistribution of metal-carbon bonds so that half of the metal-carbon double bonds in the original chains become single bonds and the other half remain double bonds (Fig. 2). It may be noted that resonance hybrids between different ways of distributing these single and double bonds are clearly possible (Fig. 2). This redistribution of the metal-carbon bonding converts the doubly bridging carbons ($\mu_2\text{-C}$) of the original $=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{}$ chains into triply bridging carbons ($\mu_3\text{-C}$). The repeating unit in this subnetwork thus may be described as $\text{MC}_{1/2}\text{C}_{3/3}^{3-}=\text{MC}_1^{3-}$.

The local environment of a Group-6 metal atom in the transition metal-carbon subnetwork of this $\text{Ln}_2\text{M}_2\text{C}_3$ structure consists of one $\text{M}=\text{C}$ bond to an interchain μ_2 -carbon bridging the original $=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{M}=\text{C}=\text{}$ chains, three metal-carbon bonds to an intrachain μ_3 -carbon now bridging three transition metal atoms, and two metal-metal bonds. The

counting of the metal electrons in the $MC_{1/2}C_{3/3}^{3-}$ unit can proceed as follows :

Neutral Cr or Mo atom	6 electrons
1/2 bridging =C=: (1/2) (4) =	2 electrons
3/3 μ_3 -carbon atom : (3/3) (4) =	4 electrons
2 M-M bonds : (2)(1) =	2 electrons
-3 charge	3 electrons
Total valence electrons per M atom	17 electrons

This 17 electron count of the central transition metal atom is one electron short of the favored 18-electron noble gas configuration. This is seemingly inconsistent with the experimentally observed Pauli paramagnetism of $Y_2Cr_2C_3$ and $Lu_2Cr_2C_3$ suggesting that the chromium atoms do not carry magnetic moments¹¹. Reehuis *et al.*¹³ suggested three-electron transition metal-metal bonds to give the transition metals the favored 18-electron configuration and required diamagnetic properties. A more plausible possibility would be alternating transition metal-metal single and double bonds in the transition metal-carbon network with averaging to metal-metal bond equivalence through resonance structures similar to the Kekulé structures in benzene (Fig. 2).

Quaternary metal carbide silicides $Ln_2M_2Si_2C$ and LnM_2SiC

The transition metal-carbon-silicon subnetwork in

$Ln_2Fe_2Si_2C$ consists of double butterfly chains linked by the linear $M=C=M$ units and long Si-Si bonds (e.g. Si-Si = 2.66 Å in $Dy_2Fe_2Si_2C$)¹⁴ as depicted in Fig. 3a. The individual Fe_2Si_2 butterfly units contain four Fe-Si bonds (~2.3 Å) and one Fe-Fe bond (~2.86 Å). The repeating unit in this subnetwork can be considered to be $FeSi_{3/3}C_{1/2}^{3-}$ with a locally six-coordinate iron atom (i.e. ignoring any Fe-Ln interactions) with one short bond (1.81 Å) to carbon corresponding to an Fe=C double bond, three bonds (~2.3 Å) to silicon, and two Fe-Fe bonds (2.86 Å). The silicon atoms can be considered to be locally four-coordinate forming one of the relatively long interchain Si-Si bonds and three Si-Fe bonds. After allowing for the single electron required from each silicon atom for its Si-Si bond, three valence electrons from each silicon atom are left for the Si-Fe bonds. This leads to the favorable 18-electron noble gas configuration for each iron atom in the $FeSi_{3/3}C_{1/2}^{3-}$ repeating units of $Ln_2Fe_2Si_2C$ as follows :

Neutral iron atom	8 electrons
1/2 bridging =C=: (1/2) (4) =	2 electrons
3/3 silicon atom from a \rightarrow Si-Si \leftarrow unit : (3/3) (3) =	3 electrons
2 Fe-Fe bonds : (2)(1) =	2 electrons
-3 charge	3 electrons
Total valence electrons per Fe atom	18 electrons

A similar 18-electron noble gas configuration can be analo-

Fig. 2. (a) The double chains of $=M=C=M=C=M=$ units used to construct the transition metal-carbon subnetwork of $Ln_2M_2C_3$, (b) linking the double chains of $=M=C=M=C=M=$ units through redistribution of the carbon-carbon bonding as well as introduction of metal-metal bonding.

Fig. 3. (a) The arrangement of the Fe_2Si_2 butterflies in the $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$ derivatives, (b) the arrangement of the Fe_2Si_2 butterflies in the LnFe_2SiC derivatives.

gously computed for the essentially isoelectronic and isostructural $\text{Th}_2\text{Re}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$ (Ref. 17) containing $\text{ReSi}_{3/3}\text{C}_{1/2}^{4-}$ repeating units. The 18-electron configuration of the iron atoms in $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$ is consistent with magnetic measurements on $\text{Lu}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$, which indicates only Pauli paramagnetism of the conduction electrons and thus no magnetic contribution from the iron atoms¹⁸.

Koo and Whangbo¹⁹ have recently reported some extended Hückel tight binding calculations on $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$ and related species. These authors do not consider the Fe-Fe bonds in these structures so that the iron atoms in their analysis are regarded as four-coordinate d^{10} metal atoms in an $(\text{Fe}=\text{C}=\text{Fe})^{8-}$ unit similar to $\text{Fe}(-\text{II})$ in $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2^{4-}$. This requires the silicon atoms to have the unusual +1 formal oxidation state (i.e. Si^+). However, assignment of formal oxidation states in the $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$ structure is confusing because of the Fe-Fe and Si-Si bonds as well as consideration of the relative electronegativity of iron and silicon. If the iron is assumed to be more electropositive than silicon in the $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$ environment, then the usual +3 and -4 oxidation states for the lanthanide and carbon, respectively, lead to a typical +2 oxidation state for iron and -3 for silicon. The -3 formal oxidation state for the silicon atoms is

not as unreasonable as it might first appear since the silicon atoms all appear as Si_2 pairs.

The structures of LnFe_2SiC like those of $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$ contain chains of Fe_2Si_2 butterflies but with the silicon atoms shared between two of the butterflies (Fig. 3b) so that the repeating unit is $\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_{2/2}$ ($=\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}$) rather than Fe_2Si_2 in accord with the overall stoichiometry. There are no direct Si-Si bonds either within the $\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_{2/2}$ butterflies or between the chains of butterflies in LnFe_2SiC in contrast to $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$. Instead the local environments of both the iron and silicon atoms in LnFe_2SiC are quite different than that of those in $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$. The silicon atoms in $\text{Ln}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_2\text{C}$ are each bonded to six iron atoms so that the repeating units in the iron-carbon-silicon subnetwork can be considered to be $\text{Fe}(\mu_6\text{-Si}_{3/6})\text{C}_{1/2}^{1.5-}$. The iron atoms in LnFe_2SiC are within bonding distance (e.g. ~ 2.8 Å) to three other iron atoms. The electron counting around an iron atom in the $\text{FeSi}_{3/6}\text{C}_{1/2}^{1.5-}$ unit can be summarized as follows :

Neutral iron atom	8 electrons
1/2 bridging $=\text{C}=\text{C}$: (1/2) (4) =	2 electrons
3/6 μ_6 -silicon atom : (3/6) (4) =	2 electrons
3 Fe-Fe bonds : (3)(1) =	3 electrons
-1.5 charge	1.5 electrons
Total valence electrons per Fe atom	16.5 electrons

This suggests that the iron atom is short of the 18-electron noble gas configuration in LnFe_2SiC in accord with the extended Hückel tight binding calculations of Koo and Whangbo¹⁹. If the lanthanide atoms are assumed to have the typical +3 oxidation state and the carbon and silicon atoms have -4 oxidation states, then the average iron oxidation state is +2.5 consistent with the LnFe_2SiC being mixed valence $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{-Fe}^{\text{III}}$ complexes. Similarly, in the isostructural ThFe_2SiC , Witte and Jeitschko¹⁵ assign the oxidation states +4, +2, -4, and -4 to the thorium, iron, silicon, and carbon atoms, respectively.

References

1. R. H. Crabtree, "The Organometallic Chemistry of the Transition Metals", 2nd ed., Wiley, New York, 1994
2. T. J. Kealy and P. L. Pauson, *Nature*, 1961, **168**, 1039
3. S. A. Miller, J. A. Tebboth and J. F. Tremaine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 632.
4. E. O. Fischer and A. Maasbol, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1964, **3**, 580
5. R. B. King, *Russ. Chem. Bull.*, 1994, **43**, 1285
6. R. B. King, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1997, **536-537**, 7
7. M. H. Gerss and W. Jeitschko, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1986, **41**, 946.
8. R. Hoffmann, J. Li and R. A. Wheeler, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 6600.

Bruce King : Structure and bonding in ternary and quaternary transition metal carbides and carbide silicides etc

- 9 W Jeitschko, G Block, G E Kahnert and R K Behrens, *J Solid State Chem* , 1990, **89**, 191
- 10 W Jeitschko and R K Behrens, *Z Metallkunde*, 1986, **77** 788
- 11 K Zeppenfeld, R Pottgen, M Reehuis, W Jeitschko and R K Behrens, *J Phys Chem Solids*, 1993, **54**, 257
- 12 M Reehuis, K Zeppenfeld, W Jeitschko and E Ressouche, *J Alloys Compounds*, 1994, **209**, 217
- 13 M Reehuis, M Gerdes, W Jeitschko B Ouladdiaf and N Stusser, *J Mag Mag Mat* , 1999, **195**, 657
- 14 L Paccard and D Paccard, *J Less-Common Met* , 1988, **136** 297
- 15 A M Witte and W Jeitschko, *J Solid State Chem* , 1994 **112**, 232
- 16 F A Cotton, "Chemical Applications of Group Theory" Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1971
- 17 T Hufken A M White and W Jeitschko, *J Alloys Compounds*, 1998, **266**, 158
- 18 R Pottgen, T Ebel, C B H Evers and W Jeitschko *J Solid State Chem* , 1995 **114** 66
- 19 H -J Koo and M H Whangbo, *Inorg Chem* , 1999 **38** 2204

